

ROLE OF VIRECHANA KARMA IN THE MANAGEMENT OF SHEETAPITTA: A CASE STUDY**Dr. Km. Preeti^{1*}, Dr. Amit Tiwari², Dr. Kamal Kishor Joshi³, Dr. Ayushi Kasyap⁴**¹P.G. Scholar, Department of Panchakarma, Patanjali Bhartiya Ayurvedic Evam Anusandhan Sansthan, Haridwar, Uttarakhand, India.²Assistant Professor, Department of Panchakarma, Patanjali Bhartiya Ayurvedic Evam Anusandhan Sansthan, Haridwar, Uttarakhand, India.³P.G. Scholar, Department of Panchakarma, Patanjali Bhartiya Ayurvedic Evam Anusandhan Sansthan, Haridwar, Uttarakhand, India.⁴P.G. Scholar, Department of Panchakarma, Patanjali Bhartiya Ayurvedic Evam Anusandhan Sansthan, Haridwar, Uttarakhand, India.***Corresponding Author: Dr. Km. Preeti**

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ABSTRACT

Sheetapitta is a *Twak vikara* described in *Ayurveda*, characterized by *kandu*, *pidika*, *daha*, and *sheeta Sparsha*. It is primarily caused by vitiation of *Vata* and *Kapha dosha* along with *Pitta dosha dushti*. Due to *Agnimandya* and *Ama* formation, the vitiated doshas manifest in the *twak*, leading to recurrent episodes affecting the patient's daily activities. In the present case study, a 32-year-old male patient presented with classical features of *Sheetapitta* for a duration of 3 months. The condition was diagnosed on the basis of *Ayurvedic lakshanas*. The patient was managed with *Shodhana chikitsa* as the planned line of treatment. The treatment protocol included *Deepana-Pachana* followed by *Purva karma* (*Snehana* and *Swedana*), and *Pardhana karma* (*Virechana karma*) and *Paschata karma* (*Samsarjana karma*) advised along with appropriate *Shamana aushadhi*. Assessment was done based on reduction in *kandu*, *pidika* and *daha*. After completion of therapy, significant relief was observed in all symptoms, with marked improvement in overall condition and no recurrence during follow up. This case study highlights the effectiveness of *Virechana karma* in eliminating vitiated *Pitta dosha* and purifying *Rakta*, thereby playing a key role in the management of *Sheetapitta*.

KEYWORDS: *Sheetapitta*, *Virechana karma*, *Shodhana*, *Twak vikara*, *Rakta dushti*.**INTRODUCTION**

Sheetapitta is described in classical *Ayurvedic Samhitas* under *Twak Vikar*. *Sheetapitta* is derived from two words “*Sheeta*” represents *Kapha* and *Vata dosha*, while “*Pitta*” refers to *Pitta dosha*. It is considered a *Tridoshaja* disorder that commonly develops after exposure to cold breeze and incompatible environmental factors. *Sheetapitta* is one of the disorders caused by *virudhahara sevan*. In *Sheetapitta*, *Vata* and *Kapha* are the primary doshas involved which causes due to *dosha prakopaaka hetu* and associated with *pitta dosha*.^[1] The condition mainly involves vitiation of *kapha* and *Vata Dosha*, along with *pitta dosha* affect the skin and blood tissues. Which then spreads throughout the body and

presenting as erythematous maculopapular eruptions over the skin. Clinical features include *Varti Damshavat Shotha*, *jwara* and *Chardi*. *Kandu* due to *Kapha* predominance, *Shula* caused by aggravated *Vata*, and *Daha* resulting from vitiated *Pitta*. Based on similarity in etiological features and clinical presentation, *Sheetapitta* can be correlated with urticaria in modern medicine.

It is described in detail in *Madhav Nidana*^[1], *Bhaishajaya Ratanavali*^[2] and *Yogratanakara*^[3] *laghutrayi*. Although specific references to *Sheetapitta* are not directly mentioned in the *Brihatrayi*, related descriptions can be identified in the context of

purvarupa^[4], Lakshana^[5] and Vyadhi.^[6] *Madhavakara* described *Sheetapitta* and *Udarda* as closely related conditions, observed in *Sheetapitta*, whereas *Kapha* predominance is more evident in *Udarda*.^[1]

In modern medicine, Urticaria is defined as recurrent hypersensitivity skin disorder characterized by transient erythematous wheals, itching and oedema that usually subside within 24 hours without leaving residual lesions. Urticaria is common dermatological condition that affects nearly 20% of the population at some point in their lifetime.^[7]

Various triggering factors such as environmental pollution, irregular dietary habits, stress, anxiety, excessive sweating, heat exposure, exercise, and altered lifestyle patterns contribute to the occurrence of urticarial.^[8] The prevalence of urticaria has increased considerably in the modern era due to rapid urbanization and un healthy lifestyle practices. Thus, *Ayurvedic* management of *Sheetapitta* focuses not only on symptomatic relief but also on correcting the underlying *Dosha* imbalance to provide effective and longterm management.

AIM AND OBJECTIVE

1. To evaluate the therapeutic effect of *Virechana karma* in the management of *Sheetapitta*.
2. To assess the efficacy of *Virechana karma* in reducing the cardinal symptoms of *Sheetapitta*.
3. To assess the overall clinical improvement in the patient after *Virechana karma* therapy.

MATERIAL AND METHODS

1. CASE REPORT

A 32-year-old male patient with medium built presented with chief complaints of elevated, reddish, irregular skin lesions with swelling since 4 months. The above complaints associated with burning sensation, itching, and discomfort, significantly affecting daily activities for the past 6 years.

The itching was observed to occur immediately after the intake of certain food items such as diet, spicy foods, citrus fruits, oily substance, and dry fruits. The symptoms were more pronounced during the night and showed partial relief in the morning.

The patient had no history of major systemic illness such as hypertension, diabetes mellitus, or thyroid disorders. Based on clinical presentation and *Ayurvedic* examination, the condition was diagnosed as *Sheetapitta*.

2. History of present illness

The patient was completely healthy before 6 years and gradually developed itching over the body followed by the appearance of reddish, elevated eruptions. The lesions were transient in nature, appearing suddenly and subsiding after some time.

The patient reported increased severity of itching and burning sensation, especially during episodes of flare-ups. The condition was recurrent, with intermittent relief but no complete resolution.

He consulted allopathic hospital and was on Antihistamine treatment for 6 years. Although the medicine provided temporary symptomatic relief. The condition recurred after stopping the medicine. Therefore, she came to ayurvedic treatment for further management.

3. Past history: Patient had no history of any systemic no medical or surgical history.

4. Personal history

- ❖ Sleep: sound
- ❖ Appetite: Normal
- ❖ Tongue: Clear
- ❖ Bowel: Clear
- ❖ Micturition: Normal pale yellow colour urine
- ❖ Occupation: Teacher

5. *Nidana*^[9]: Exposure to *Sheeta maruta* leads to vitiation of *kapha* and *vata dosha*, which subsequently associated with vitiated *pitta dosha*. The combined vitiation of all *Tridosha* circulates throughout the body and localizes in the *Twak*, resulting in the manifestation of *Sheetapitta*.

a) *Aharaja hetu*: Excessive intake of *amla*, *lavana*, *katu rasa*, *kshara*, *viruddha ahara* frequent consumption of *dadhi*, contribute to *dosha* vitiation.

b) *Viharaja hetu*: Exposure to *sheeta maruta*, insect bites, *chardi nigraha*, seasonal influence like *shishira ritu* and *vastra*, *abhushana* act as precipitating factors.

c) *Nidanaarthakara roga*: Diseases such as *Pittaja* and *Kaphaja jwara*, *Sannipataja roga*, *Unmada*, and *Adhoga amlapitta* may predispose to the development of *Sheetapitta*.

d) *Chikitsa mithya yoga*: *Vamana* and *Virachana*.

6. *Pooravarupa*^[10]

- ❖ *Pipasa* (Thirst)
- ❖ *Aruchi* (loss of appetite)
- ❖ *Hrillasa* (Nausea)
- ❖ *Dehasada* (General malaise)
- ❖ *Anga Gaurava* (A feeling of heaviness in the body)
- ❖ *Rakta lochanata* (Redness of eye)

7. *Rupa*^[11]

- ❖ *Varti Damshta Samsthana Shotha* (Inflammation characterized by insect bite)
- ❖ *Kandu Bahula* (Intense itching)
- ❖ *Toda Bahula* (Pricking type of pain)
- ❖ *Chhardi* (Vomiting)
- ❖ *Jvara* (fever)
- ❖ *Vidaha* (Burning sensation)

8. Samprapti Ghataka

- ❖ *Dosha: Tridosha*
- ❖ *Agni: Mandagni*
- ❖ *Vyadhimarga: Bahya*
- ❖ *Dushya: Rasa, Rakta*
- ❖ *Srotas: Rasavaha, Raktavaha*
- ❖ *Srotodushtiprakara: Vimarga gamana*
- ❖ *Udbhava Sthana: Aamashaya*
- ❖ *Vyakti Sthana: Twak*
- ❖ *Svabhava: Ashukari*

9. General Examination

- ❖ Pulse: 86/min.
- ❖ BP: 130/80mmHg
- ❖ RR: 22/min.
- ❖ Temp: 98.6°F
- ❖ Weight: 70Kg

- ❖ Height: 6feet7inch

10. Asthavidha Parkisha of patient

- ❖ *Nadi: Pitta-kapha predominant*
- ❖ *Mala: Malavrodh*
- ❖ *Mutra: Samyak*
- ❖ *Jivha: Aalipta*
- ❖ *Shabda: Spashta*
- ❖ *Sparsha: Anushna-sheeta*
- ❖ *Druk: Samyak*
- ❖ *Aakruti: Madhyam*

Assessment Criteria

The assessment of the patient was carried out based on the improvement in subjective parameters, namely *shotha, kandu, toda* and *vidaha*.

S.no.	Lakshana	Mild	Moderate	Severe
1.	<i>Shotha</i> (Inflammation)	1	2	3
2.	<i>Kandu</i> (Itching)	1	2	3
3.	<i>Toda</i> (Pricking sensation)	1	2	3
4.	<i>Vidaha</i> (Burning sensation)	1	2	3

Treatment plan**1. Purva karma****A. Deepana-Pachana:** 2 days.

S.NO.	MEDICINE	DOSE	TIME	ANUPANA
1.	<i>Chitrakadi vati</i> ^[12]	2 tablets	Before meal, TDS	Lukewarm water
2.	<i>Panchakol churna</i>	½ teaspoon	After meal, TDS	Lukewarm water

Purpose: To improve agni and digest ama, preparing the body for *snehpana*.

B. Snehpana

Drug – *Panchatikta ghrita*^[13] (Duration- morning hours).

DAY	1	2	3	4
DOSE	30ml	60ml	100ml	150ml

C. Sarvanga Abhyanga

Drug: *Mulethi taila* and *kaya kalpa taila*.

Duration: 4 days.

D. Sarvanga vashapa swadana

Duration: 4 days.

Purpose: Liquification and movement of *dosha* to *kostha*.

2. Paradhana karma

Procedure: *Virachana*

Drug: *Trivrata avleha* 70gm and *Draksha kashaya* 200ml

Vegas: Number of *vegas* 18

Shuddhi: *Madhyama, Kaphaant darshana*, was characterized by whitish liquid stools, confirming proper elimination of vitiated *Dosha*.

3. Paschata karma**A. Samsarjana karma:** 5 days.

<i>Peya</i>	<i>Vilepi</i>	<i>Akrita yusha</i>	<i>Krita yusha</i>
2 times (E, M)	2 times (E, M)	2 times (E, M)	2 times (E, M)

OBSERVATION AND RESULTS

The patient was observed carefully during all phases of treatment, including *Purva karma, Pradhana karma*, and

Paschata karma, and the outcomes were assessed based on subjective parameters.

The patient showed significant clinical improvement following *Virechana karma* within 10 days. There was marked reduction in itching, burning sensation, pricking sensation and inflammation. Overall improvement in

skin appearance, improvement in *agni*, patient experienced *laghuta*, improvement in *nidra*, absence of recurrence. Overall, the patient showed satisfactory clinical improvement without any complications.

S.No.	Symptoms	Before treatment	After treatment
1	<i>Shotha</i> (inflammation)	3	0
2	<i>Kandu</i> (Itching)	3	0
3	<i>Toda</i> (Pricking sensation)	3	0
4	<i>Vidaha</i> (Burning sensation)	3	0

Pathya-Apathya Ahara^[14]

Pathya Ahara: *Madhu, Mudga yusha, Kulattha yusha, Ushnodaka, karkotaka Shaka, Karkotaka Shaka, Moolak Yusha, Dadima Phala, Shigru Shaka, Jerena Shali, Jangala Mamsa.*

Apathya Ahara: *Ksheera Vikarani, Chhardi Nigraha, Ikshu vikarani, Divaswapna, Matsya, Naveena Madhya, Atapa sevana, Virudhahara, Vyavaya.*

BEFORE

AFTER

पतंजलि आयुर्वेद चिकित्सालय
PATANJALI AYURVEDA HOSPITAL

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 पंजीकरण संख्या Reg. No. 54731-2025 चिकित्सक Vd. Dr. Amit Tiwari दिनांक Date 24/09/2025...
 विभाग Deptt. PANCHKARMA वार्षिक संख्या Annual No. PA-10218-2025 कक्ष संख्या Room No.0...
 रोगी : श्री/श्रीमती Patient : Mr./Mrs. Nishant Rajput आयु Age 32.Y. लिंग Sex Male.....
 पता Address Sohasanpur Chamra Po- Mandavar, Bijnor, Uttar Pradesh, India
 फोन Landline No. : मो. Mobile No. : 9897971853 ईमेल E-mail :

CONCLUSION

Virechana karma proved to be an effective therapeutic intervention in the management of *Sheetapitta*. The procedure resulted in significant reduction in key symptoms such as *Kandu*, *Daha*, *Shotha* and *Toda*, along with decreased frequency of *Sheetapitta* episodes.

The attainment of *Madhyama Shuddhi* with indicated proper elimination of vitiated *pitta dosha* and overall physical well-being further indication restoration of physiological balance.

Hence, *Virechana karma* can be concluded as a safe, effective, and reliable therapeutic modality in the management of *Sheetapitta*, with promising results in symptoms control and prevention of recurrence.

DISCUSSION

In this case, *Virechana karma* showed marked clinical improvement in the patient suffering from *Sheetapitta*. Noticeable relief in symptoms was observed within 15 days of treatment. The attainment of *Samyak Shuddhi*, along with reduction in symptoms severity, indicates proper elimination of vitiated *Tridosha*.

Sustained improvement observed during follow-up suggests the role of *Virechana* not only in symptomatic management but also in preventing recurrence. Therefore, *Virechana karma* can be considered an effective modality in the management of *Sheetapitta*.

This single case study concludes that Ayurvedic management with *Virechana karma* provides excellent results in the treatment of *Sheetapitta* by effectively eliminating vitiated *Dosha*, improving *Agni*, and restoring physiological balance.

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